

Facilitator Reflection on online Action-learning

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Reflection workshops are an integral part of action-learning because they bring valuable insights on the educational activity and feed into the improvement of learning methodology; learning sources and tools; assessment methods and the role of the facilitator(s). Two reflection workshops following the action-learning FoodFactory-4-Us international online student competitions in 2019 and 2020 brought together 2 and 5 facilitators, respectively, for half day online reflection workshops addressing quantitative and qualitative aspects of the 4.5 month online competition course. A third workshop in March 2021 will have 3 facilitators follow the same methodology. The facilitators assessed the transition to action-learning based on facilitator activities: the shift from teaching to learning and from knowledge to competence. They used a Likert scale of 1 to 10 to individually rank the shifts from (1) lecture hall to a diversity of learning arenas; (2) lecturing to peer learning; (3) syllabus to supporting literature/a variety of learning sources; (4) written exam to a variety of assessment methods; and (5) lecturer to learning facilitator. Average rankings indicated that (4) shift to a variety of assessment methods and (5) role of the facilitator were the highest rated, 8.6 and 7.4, respectively. Facilitators also wrote responses to reflective questions on what could further push the shift to action learning and specifically how this could be accomplished. A discourse analysis was carried out through inductive coding of these qualitative data using NVIVO 12 software to produce a word cloud indicating the most commonly used phrases. Interaction among teams, and learning methods fostering interaction and collaboration across teams were the improvement factors most frequently stated. Most commonly stated methods were to actively facilitate questions during online trainings and to move further away from typical webinar formats where linear learning prevailed. Reflection workshops have become an integral part of FoodFactory-4-Us online competition cycles providing valuable insights into the planning of these ongoing competitions